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Towards A Universal Humanism : Gandhian Philosophy On Equality Beyond Social Divides

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Abstract

The concepts of non-violence (*ahimsa*) and unwavering commitment to human equality, irrespective of caste, class, or gender, stand at the heart of Gandhian philosophy. This paper explores the philosophical foundations of Gandhian equality as an expression of universal humanism, which may have been inspired in part by his contemporary Rabindranath Tagore. However, Gandhi's thought remains original and distinct in perspective. Drawing on his writings, speeches, and major movements, this study examines how Gandhi's critique of caste discrimination, economic exploitation, and patriarchal norms was rooted in his moral philosophy anchored in *ahimsa* (non-violence) and *satyagraha* (truth force). It argues that Gandhian philosophy embodies the ideal of universal humanism, an indispensable foundation for peace at societal, national, and global levels.

Keywords Gandhi, Equality, Universal Humanism, Caste, Class, Gender, Philosophy.

Introduction

Gandhian philosophy has played a crucial role in shaping modern Indian and global thought. It offers a moral and spiritual framework essential for the realization of universal humanism. Literary and philosophical evidence demonstrates that the entire structure of Gandhian thought promotes humanism through individual transformation. Present era is gaining momentum to create more and more miseries in human life. Human race has got new challenge to cope with the mental health of the masses. Human beings appear to be trapped in the invisible web of extreme materialism, arrogant and dominating politics, insensitive and anthropocentric attitude, etc. But Gandhi recommends not to lose faith in humanity.

His philosophy is deeply rooted in principles of equality and social justice, emerging from his spiritual and ethical vision. Gandhi's conception of human equality arises from his doctrines of *ahimsa* and *satyagraha*. His philosophy represents both a critique of entrenched hierarchies and an aspirational call for a more humane world order. This article explores Gandhi's philosophical approach to bridging caste, class, and gender divides through his ethical and moral framework. Although the Gandhian framework is neither strictly epistemological nor metaphysical, it serves as a powerful means to establish a just and cohesive socio-political order. His philosophy advances the ideal of universal humanism, envisioning a society in which all individuals can coexist in harmony. Moreover, it firmly rejects the perpetuation of caste- and gender-based discrimination, advocating equality as the foundation of progress in the society.

Objective of study

The objective of the present study is to explore the philosophical and contemporary relevance of Gandhian Philosophy from the perspective of universal humanism. Gandhi's sublime thoughts are deeply grounded in the notions of *ahimsa* (non-violence) and *satyagraha* (truth force). In this context, the objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To explore the philosophical foundations of Gandhian philosophy from the perspective of universal humanism.
2. To examine Gandhi's critique of caste, class and gender-based divides.
3. To work out a model for the relationship between individual transformation and social reconstruction in Gandhi's vision, showing how personal morality and inner purification serve as prerequisites for establishing external harmony.
4. To explore the humanistic perspective of Gandhian sublime thoughts.
5. To situate Gandhian universal humanism within the broader tradition of Indian philosophical traditions

Review of Literature

Gandhian philosophy has inspired numerous scholars across diverse fields of study. Scholars from philosophy, political science, and related disciplines have explored Gandhi's doctrines of *ahimsa* (non-violence) and *satyagraha* (truth-force) from various perspectives. The literature on Gandhi's thought reveals a consistent concern with human dignity, equality, and the moral regeneration of society. These principles are essential to doing justice to the concept of universal humanism.

Raghavan N. Iyer's *The Moral and Political Thought of Mahatma Gandhi* (1973) stands as a major work on Gandhi's ethical vision. Iyer's interpretation of Gandhi's philosophy is remarkable, presenting it as an experiment in living that emphasizes self-discipline, truth, and compassion as instruments of social harmony. Bhikhu Parekh (1997) redefined political action as a form of ethical practice in his book *Gandhi: A Very Short Introduction*. J. Parel's *Gandhi's Philosophy and the Quest for Harmony* (2003) explores Gandhi's thought as a pursuit of both ontological and social harmony. Parel interprets Gandhi's principle of *sarvodaya* as an expression of universal humanism, rooted in the recognition of the interconnectedness of all beings.

In *Gandhi and the Challenge of Religious Diversity* (2006), M. Chatterjee examines Gandhi's profound reflections on religion and spirituality. B. Chakrabarty's *Gandhi: A Complete Introduction* (2014) situates Gandhi's philosophy within the broader political and historical framework of modern India. Thomas Weber (1992), in *Gandhi as Disciple and Mentor*, explores Gandhi's relationships with his followers and the transformative power of his ethics.

Many scholars of philosophy have also drawn attention to the metaphysical dimensions of Gandhian ethics, as reflected in his *Autobiography: The Story of My Experiments with Truth* (1927) and *Satyagraha in South Africa* (1928). Scholars such as Eknath Easwaran have highlighted the resemblances between Buddhist and Gandhian thought, although this interpretation remains debatable. Overall, the existing literature demonstrates that Gandhian philosophy integrates ethics with the social framework, envisioning a society beyond caste, class, and gender-based divisions.

Main Text

Gandhian Philosophy Reflecting Equality

Ahimsa as a Dynamic Force

In the Gandhian system, *ahimsa* (non-violence) is the foundational principle of peace. Contrary to popular interpretation, *ahimsa* is not merely the absence of violence; rather, it is an active moral force and a form of power (Gandhi, 1993). It requires refraining not only from violent actions but also from harboring violent thoughts based on religion, caste, or gender.

In the contemporary context, where divisions persist, Gandhi's philosophy of treating all human beings as equals remains under-practiced. Without practicing equality, the realization of universal humanism becomes impossible. Gandhi's vision of humanism thus emerges as an indirect consequence of practicing *ahimsa* through *satyagraha* (Parekh, 1997).

It is argued that central to Gandhian humanism is the transformation of the individual. Equality and non-violence must begin at the personal level. Social transformation, therefore, is possible only when individuals embody these principles. However, Gandhi observed that people often expect society to change without recognizing their own responsibility as integral components of that society. Gandhi viewed peace as multi-dimensional. Inner peace arises from cultivating non-violence in thought, emotion, and action. Once inner purification is achieved, external harmony naturally follows. Gandhi emphasized personal transformation by living as an example, notably through his practice of celibacy and simplicity (Iyer, 1973).

He believed conscience to be the innate guide that differentiates right from wrong. When individuals commit unethical acts, their conscience evokes guilt i.e. provided they remain self-aware. Gandhi's famous dictum, "Live as if you were to die tomorrow," reflects his focus on present-moment awareness (*Young India*, May 25, 1921). Living in the present,

he argued, preserves energy for constructive action, whereas dwelling on the past or future leads to anxiety and moral stagnation.

Understanding equality purifies thought, reshapes behaviour, and transforms attitude. One of Gandhi's central objectives was to promote friendliness and compassion through continuous practice of non-violence. He claims that the acid test of non-violence is that enemies will have to be finally converted into friends. Such is the power of practicing non-violence (*Harijan*, November 12, 1938).

Force Of Truth (*Satyagraha*) And Universal Humanism

Satyagraha as Truth Force

Satyagraha is a revolutionary concept referring to the power of truth and love. Often misinterpreted as "passive resistance" (Weber, 1992), it actually signifies active moral engagement rooted in truth. Gandhi claimed that *satyagraha* was not merely a political strategy but a way of life "living the truth" itself (Gandhi, 1928). Now this phrase is directly derived from the position of Indian Philosophy that an individual has to experience self-realization or *moksha* to make his life meaningful. Only then the purpose of his existence may be realized. Similar position is maintained by other schools of Indian Philosophy like Buddhism, and Jainism, Vedanta, etc.

For Gandhi, *satyagraha* embodies *soul force* which is a recognition of the unity of all human beings. It resonates with the Buddhist notion of *Brahmakaya* or the universal body. Like the Buddha, Gandhi advocated cultivating compassion and empathy for all living beings (Parel, 2003). Thus, *satyagraha* serves both as a method of conflict resolution and as a vehicle for realizing universal humanism.

In Gandhian thought, evil must be opposed, but the one who has done the evil must not be dehumanized. He maintained the person who is practicing *satyagraha* must never forget the distinction between evil and the one who did the evil (*Young India*, August 8, 1929). Gandhi argues that violence is intrinsically immoral regardless of intention or context.

He likened evil to a disease that must be cured rather than condemned. "The essence of non-violence technique is that it seeks to liquidate antagonisms but not antagonists themselves" (*Harijan*, April 29, 1939). Through such an approach, Gandhi envisioned peaceful coexistence amidst diversity.

Equality, for Gandhi, stemmed from recognizing the essential unity of humanity. His *ahimsa* demanded not only the absence of physical violence but also the eradication of structural and psychological violence rooted in casteism, classism, and gender bias (Parekh, 1997). *Satyagraha* thus emphasized moral resistance without dehumanizing the opponent, seeking to reveal the inherent worth of all individuals.

Bridging Caste, Class, And Gender Divides

Gandhi's lifelong struggle against untouchability represented a cornerstone of his ethical philosophy. By renaming the so-called "untouchables" as *Harijans* ("children of God"), Gandhi affirmed their dignity (Chatterjee, 2006). Some people criticized him for not entirely dismantling the caste system but they fail to realize that people must also participate in total abolition of the caste system. He can only play the role of leader, and make people aware about the evil of caste system. his efforts toward temple entry and inter-dining symbolized radical challenges to ritual purity and social exclusion.

Economic inequality, for Gandhi, was another form of violence. He proposed *Sarvodaya* (welfare of all) and the doctrine of trusteeship where wealth is held not as private property but as a trust for society's benefit (Parel, 2003). Unlike Marxist materialism, Gandhi's approach was ethical and nonviolent, emphasizing cooperation over conflict. Programs like *khadi* and village industries were intended to restore self-reliance and dignity to rural India.

Though a product of his time, Gandhi's thought opened new avenues for women in public life. He regarded women as embodiments of moral strength and non-violence, central to his movements (Chakrabarty, 2014). Gandhi opposed child marriage, dowry, and *purdah*, and advocated women's education and participation in national life. His conception of gender equality was thus inseparable from his moral vision of truth and *ahimsa*. Thus, Gandhian philosophy is deeply concerned with creating a society which runs on the

principle of social justice and equality. Indian society was deeply suffering from disease of caste and caste-based struggle. Gandhi observed it particularly while he was pursuing his "Champaran Satyagraha" in the state of Bihar. The caste system is deeply rooted in this state. He observed that people were unable to think beyond the caste and the class. Even a person belonging to the lower caste can't sit by the side of the person belonging to the upper class. These practices created much pain in the heart of Mahatma Gandhi. I argue that this is one of the main reasons why he dedicated his life for the welfare of mankind. His thoughts were not confined to India only. In many countries of the world like South Africa his work is still remembered and their social framework is deeply influenced by Gandhian thoughts.

Contemporary Relevance

In an era marked by persistent caste discrimination, economic inequality, and gender injustice, Gandhi's vision remains profoundly relevant. His integrative approach offers a timeless framework for addressing global concerns such as human rights, social inclusion, and ecological balance. Gandhian universalism continues to inspire non-violent social transformation across cultures and continents. In the present scenario, Gandhian philosophy is more relevant than ever before. There is an urgent need to understand and practice the principle of Ahimsa in its truest sense. Contemporary media practices, often driven by the pursuit of higher TRPs, have normalized verbal aggression and sensationalism, which may be considered a form of word-based violence. However, as citizens of a country known as "the land of Gandhi," it is imperative to practice *ahimsa* not only in deeds but also in thoughts and speech. We must exercise utmost care in our choice of language which echoes the Buddha's concept of *Samyak Vāk* (right speech). The right speech is the essential component of the Noble Eightfold Path (Dhammapada 5).

The relevance of Gandhian philosophy extends to all vital domains of human existence, including environmental preservation and industrial development. The notion of universal humanism inherently encompasses the protection of the natural environment, as it calls for a heightened sensitivity and moral awareness among individuals toward all forms of life. Nature must be safeguarded so that every human being can continue to enjoy the planet's flora and fauna, which ultimately benefits humanity as a whole. Gandhian thought emphasizes that human beings are not separate from other living entities; rather, all life forms are part of an integrated and interdependent existence. This interconnectedness that we identify is essential for the realization of a just, compassionate, and sustainable world.

Conclusion

Gandhi's philosophy of equality transcended politics; it was an ethical vision of universal humanism. By simultaneously addressing caste, class, and gender, Gandhi developed a holistic conception of justice rooted in truth and nonviolence. His insight that authentic equality arises from recognizing shared human dignity continues to guide philosophical and ethical thought.

He reminded humanity that only individual change can bring social change. In other words, true peace begins with individual transformation. *Satyagraha*, as both an epistemological and metaphysical concept, represents the law of love as a universal law like the law of gravitation.

In an age of violence and alienation, Gandhian philosophy advocates the faith in universal humanism. His vision calls for inner transformation as the foundation for global harmony and enduring peace. Hence, his philosophy is par excellence and promotes the notion of equality among all human beings, irrespective of caste, creed, or gender. Gandhian thought is both sublime and timeless, and there is an urgent need to understand and practice it in contemporary society.

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